

HETEROGENEOUS EQUILIBRIA. THE TERNARY SYSTEM OF POTASSIUM NITRATE, AMMONIUM NITRATE AND WATER

BY RAM CHAND AND JANRSH CHANDRA JAIN

Ammonium nitrate cannot be separated in pure state from solutions containing even small quantities of potassium nitrate while potassium nitrate can be separated in a pure state when its concentration in the solutions is more than 25%.

The ternary system of potassium nitrate, ammonium nitrate and water has been studied by Bahl and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 441) who report that both the salts can be separated out in the pure state from mixtures of the two, there being no formation of mixed crystals. While working on the reversible salt pair system of ammonium nitrate, potassium sulphate and water it was found that the ternary system reported above required a fresh investigation.

Isothermal relationships have been investigated at 25°. At this temperature exploration was carried out by means of Schrienemakers's well known 'residue method'. Owing, however, to the formation of solutions this method was not sufficient to fix the composition of the solid phases with certainty. Supplementary experiments for isolation and analysis of the solid phases were carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experiments were conducted in a thermostat maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ with the help of an electrical thermoregulator. Definite proportions of the two salts were mixed with water, sealed in bulb tubes and then shaken for 48 hours. The seals were then broken and the solution separated from the solid with the help of pipettes heated to 25°. Both the solid and the liquid were analysed separately.

For supplementary examination of solid phases, solutions were allowed to evaporate at the temperature of the thermostat until a small crop of crystals appeared. The crystals were separated under suction on a sintered glass funnel placed in a hot water funnel through which water at 25° was being circulated and they were washed with little water and dried rapidly on filter paper pads.

Ammonium nitrate was estimated by determining the quantity of ammonia in the solution by distilling with alkali. Potassium nitrate was determined by finding out total nitrate by ferrous sulphate method, being frequently checked against Lunge's nitrometer method, and after subtracting the nitrate for ammonium nitrate the quantity of potassium nitrate was calculated. Water was always estimated by difference.

The composition of the solutions and wet solids obtained by Schreinemakers's method are presented in the following table.

The points representing the solubilities of pure ammonium nitrate and potassium nitrate in water are taken from Seidells' 'Dictionary of Solubilities.'

These results are plotted graphically on the triangular co-ordinate system in Fig. 1.

The results show clearly that pure ammonium nitrate does not separate out from solutions containing even very small quantities of potassium nitrate, while potassium nitrate separates out in a pure state from solutions containing more than 25% of potassium nitrate. It is surprising that the formation of mixed crystals in this system was missed by Bahl and Singh (*loc. cit.*). This is evidently due to the fact that they have tried only 5 compositions and thus ignored some vital points. The results have been confirmed by isothermal evaporation of solutions rich in ammonium nitrate. The base of the triangular co-ordinate diagram is formed of the binary system $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-KNO}_3$ which has been studied very

TABLE I
System NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 and water. Composition by weight.

H_2O	Solution		H_2O	KNO_3	Rest	NH_4NO_3	Solid NH_4NO_3
	KNO_3	NH_4NO_3					
31'90%	...	68'10%	...	...	...	...	} Mixed crystals
32'14	1'742%	66'12	23'19%	2'606%	74'20%		
31'66	3'724	64'63	20'17	4'773	75'06		
31'48	6'288	62'23	21'25	10'880	80'87		
31'76	6'640	61'59	23'09	8'860	68'05		
31'90	8'870	59'22	17'97	13'78	68'24		
31'04	12'25	56'70	19'35	17'60	63'05		
31'16	13'03	55'81	20'64	18'06	61'30		
31'20	16'62	52'18	16'13	33'60	50'27		
31'49	17'72	50'79	18'88	35'03	46'09		
31'42	17'82	50'76	17'10	35'56	47'34		
31'07	18'66	50'27	22'99	27'62	49'39		
32'40	19'00	48'60	18'00	51'00	31'00		
38'25	19'18	41'94	22'14	53'47	24'39	} KNO_3	
41'60	20'32	38'08	21'20	56'53	22'27		
43'25	20'92	35'84	20'61	60'53	20'24		
52'26	22'37	25'37	31'22	49'05	17'23		
62'86	25'95	11'19	41'80	49'87	8'33		
72'90	27'10	...	...	...	...		

extensively by Perman and Saunders (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 128, 841), Janecke (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1928, 41, 916), Janecke, Hamacher and Rahlfs (*Z. anorg. Chem.* 1932, 206, 357) and lastly by Glass, Laybourn and Magdlin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 199) who have deduced

the form of this binary system NH_4NO_3 , KNO_3 and $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and have concluded that the two salts are isomorphous, capable of forming mixed crystals and that there is no evidence that pure ammonium nitrate separates from mixtures rich in this salt. Our results are in agreement with their conclusions and it is quite evident that the results obtained by Bahl and Surjit Singh (*loc. cit.*) are erroneous.

FIG. 1

Thanks are due to Dr. S. D. Muzaffar for guidance and keen interest he has taken in the work.